

Research

The Impact of Non-Bank Financial Institutions on Economic Growth in Mongolia

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Abstract: In recent decades, the structure of financial intermediation has changed dramatically. Banks' stake in the financial system is decreasing, while non-banks' involvement is expanding, and this tendency is particularly noticeable in Mongolia. The shifting structure of financial intermediation has piqued monetary authorities' interest, as it has the potential to alter the way monetary policy is conveyed to the economy. The purpose of this study is to look at the impact of non-banking financial institutions on Mongolian monetary policy transmission. Using time series data from 2000 to 2022 (<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/af1a0293254ac2e448cafa165c669d88-0070012022/original/MEU-2022-April-ENG.pdf>), this research intends to empirically investigate the development impact of Non-Bank Financial Intermediaries on Mongolian economic growth. Non-bank financial activities are defined as services provided by a business entity that has secured a license from the Bank of Mongolia, as defined in article 7.1 of the present law. The study investigates the existence of a long run equilibrium link between NBFIs and economic development using a limited testing technique to cointegration and an error correcting mechanism. The analysis discovers that NBFIs and real per capita income have a long-run cointegrating connection. According to economic theory, solid and efficient financial systems—banks, equities markets, and bond markets—that route capital to its most productive uses promote economic growth. Since the early 1990s, the financial systems of the region have developed deeper and more diversified, according to the data. Financial development has a strong beneficial effect on growth, especially in emerging nations, according to a more rigorous econometric analysis of 125 countries' panel data. The findings also show that the influence of financial development on regional growth is similar to that of other regions, and that the impact has reduced since the Asian financial crisis. Overall, our research supports the assumption that continued financial sector development is important for developing Asia's post-crisis growth. However, the primary role of financial sector development in growth is likely to change away from mobilizing funds and so increasing investment volume and toward improving investment efficiency and thereby contributing to improved overall productivity. The study suggests that the role of NBFIs and their value to the economic growth process are more pronounced in countries with more developed financial systems. As a result, strategies aimed at strengthening the NBFIs sector are required, considering their ability to contribute to economic growth.

Keywords: Non-bank financial intermediaries, bounds testing approach, stability, economic growth, cointegration, Mongolia.

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1. Introduction

Many empirical studies have sought to analyze and quantify the role of financial institutions to economic growth (see Ang 2008; Baltagi, Demetriades, and Law 2009; De Gregorio and Guidotti 1995; Jalilian and Kirkpatrick 2002;

King and Levine 1993a, 1993b; Odedokun 1996). Authors in these studies use aggregate financial or monetary variables like the M2 to GDP ratio (King and Levine 1993a), the M3 to GDP ratio (Khan and Senhadji 2000), gross domestic savings to GDP (Hassan and al. 2011), banks' deposits or assets over GDP, and private credit by banks over GDP (Levine, Loayza, and Beck 2000) or liquid liabilities to GDP to measure financial development..

It is well acknowledged in the academic literature that an efficient and well-developed financial system is important for influencing economic growth. The positive effects of financial development on growth are basically credited to the functions it plays particularly in the mobilization and allocation of resources needed to undertake productive investment activities by various economic agents. Theoretical literature argued that the increased availability of financial instruments and institutions greatly reduces transaction and information costs in the economy which in turn influences savings rate, investment decisions and undertaking of technological innovations. A large number of empirical works (e.g., King and Levine, 1993; Levine, 1997, 2003; Neusser and Kugler, 1998; Beck, Levine, and Loayza 2000; Abma and Fase, 2003; Luintel and Khan, 1999; Odedokun, 1996; Rioja and Valev, 2004 etc.) have also tested the finance-growth relationship employing different methodological techniques using different indicators of financial development in cross-country or time series studies. The empirical findings are generally in consensus that a well-functioning and efficient financial system has beneficial impacts on economic growth.

The majority of prior research has focused on either banking or stock market development. The finance-growth nexus literature has employed these two financial system sectors as proxies for financial development. Non-bank financial intermediaries (henceforth NBFIs) have emerged as one of the most important sub-sectors in the development of the financial system, and their interaction with economic activity has been largely disregarded. The relationship between the development of NBFIs and economic growth has not been adequately investigated empirically. Although in recent, there have been some studies (e.g., Impavido and Musalem, 2000; Impavido, Musalem and Tressel, 2003; Harichandra and Thangavelu, 2004; Devis and Hu, 2004 etc.) attempted to examine the association between NBFIs and economic growth, they mainly focused on the developed economies (e.g., OECD) and concentrated disproportionately on the contractual savings (pension and insurance funds) or only on the pension funds. This is despite the fact that in many rapidly growing economies, the NBFIs in various forms have also been seen fast-expanding to complement the services of the financial system.

The literature suggests that there might be both direct and indirect links between NBFI development and economic growth (Alderman & Yemtsov 2013; Davis & Hu 2008; Haiss & Sumegi 2008; Holzmann 1997; Liang & Reichert 2012; Meng & Pfau 2010; Nassr & Wehinger 2014; Sufian & Majid 2009; Vitas 1997). It can be direct in the sense that NBFIs can have a direct impact on savings, investment, risk allocation, and total factor productivity, resulting in increased economic growth. On the contrary, the linkage can be indirect through the influence of NBFIs on the development of banks and capital (stock and bond) markets, which, in turn, influences economic growth (Haiss & Sumegi 2008; Meng & Pfau 2010; Sufian & Majid 2009). However, if the growth in the volume of loanable funds is too rapid and is not properly regulated and monitored, it may create conditions susceptible to a financial crisis. Liang and Reichert (2012) accordingly warn that if NBFIs are not properly regulated, they allow excessive risk appetite which may have disastrous consequences for both the financial sector and the economy.

Institutions that pool risk. Insurance firms insure economic risks such as death, disease, property damage or loss, and other types of loss. They offer a speculative guarantee of financial protection in the event of a loss. Life insurance and general insurance are the two primary categories of insurance companies. General insurance is often short-term, whereas life insurance is a longer contract that expires when the insured passes away. Life and property insurance are both offered to all members of the community. Insurance businesses have a high level of information efficiency due to the nature of the sector (companies must access a profusion of information to assess the risk in each unique instance). Insurance companies insure against the financial loss that might result from the insured's untimely death. Every term, the insured will pay a set amount as an insurance premium. Because the likelihood of death rises with age but premiums remain constant, the insured overpays in the early years and underpays later. The cash value of the

insurance policy is the overpayment in the early years of the agreement. Institutions for contract savings. Individuals can invest in collective investment vehicles in a fiduciary rather than a principal role through contractual savings institutions (also known as institutional investors). Individuals and firms pool their resources to participate in a variety of equities, debt, and derivatives promises through collective investment vehicles. The individual, on the other hand, owns stock in the CIV rather than the investments it makes. Mutual funds and private pension plans are the two most common contractual savings institutions. Open-end and closed-end mutual funds are the two most common forms of mutual funds. By allowing the public to buy new shares at any moment, open-end funds generate new investments. Shareholders can sell their shares back to the open-end fund at the net asset value to liquidate their holdings. In an IPO, closed-end funds issue a set number of shares. By selling their shares on a stock exchange, shareholders profit from the value of their assets. Mutual funds are classified according to the type of investments they make. Some funds, for example, invest in high-risk, high-return securities, while others concentrate on tax-exempt securities. Others focus on speculative trading (hedge funds), a particular industry, or cross-border investments. Pension funds are mutual funds that prevent investors from accessing their money until after a specific date. In exchange, huge tax incentives are given to pension funds in order to encourage working people to set aside a portion of their present income for a time when they are no longer employed (retirement income). Financial institutions that are not banks. Broker-dealer institutions that quote both a buy and sell price for an asset held in inventory are known as market makers. Equities, government and corporate debt, derivatives, and foreign currencies are examples of such assets. When a market maker receives an order, it sells from its inventory or makes a buy to compensate for the loss in inventory. The bid-offer spread, or the difference between buying and selling quotes, is how the market-maker generates money. Market makers make any asset in their inventory more liquid. Sectoral financiers offer a limited range of financial services to a certain industry. Leasing businesses, for example, provide equipment financing, while real estate lenders supply funds to potential homeowners. In comparison to other specialist sectoral financiers, leasing businesses have two distinct benefits. Because they possess the leased equipment as part of their collateral agreement, they are somewhat protected from the danger of default. Leasing companies also benefit from advantageous tax treatment on equipment purchases. Brokers (both securities and mortgage), management consultants, and financial advisors are examples of other financial service providers. They charge a fee for each service. Financial service providers, for the most part, improve the informational investor's efficiency. Brokers, on the other hand, provide a transactional service through which an investor can liquidate existing assets. In this study, the authors explore the impact of NBFIs on economic growth by extending Odedokun's (1996) neoclassical growth model. As mentioned above, Liang and Reichert (2007) found evidence that a shift in the relative importance of bank-based and market-based financial sector factors takes place as the level of economic development expands. Thus, to capture these differences, the estimation sample will be divided into developed and emerging market countries with the expectation that different factors and the relative importance of common factors will vary by the level of economic development. Furthermore, the impact of various types of financial institutions might potentially be highly correlated. To address these high correlations, a principal components analysis is conducted to reduce the number of variables in the model and to transform a set of correlated variables into a set of orthogonal variables. Furthermore, the unique impact of NBFIs on economic growth can be estimated by controlling the impact of commercial banks and central banks' economic growth model.

Our panel dataset covers the reform era from 1995 to 2003, which helps to mitigate the negative impact of financial reforms on growth. The issue that financial reforms were implemented precisely when the economy was projected to boom should be less of a concern. Furthermore, growth rates have been declining over time as the Chinese government has orchestrated a "soft landing" of the economy. The civil code, company law, banking law, licensing law, and any other essential legislative actions make up the legislation governing nonbank financial activities.

2. Results

2.1. Non Banking financial institution

A nonbank financial institution (NBFIs) is a financial institution that does not have a full banking license and is therefore unable to take public deposits. Alternative financial services, such as investment (both collective and individual), risk pooling, financial consultation, brokering, money transmission, and check cashing, are all available through NBFIs. Consumer financing is provided via NBFIs (along with licensed banks). Examples of nonbank financial institutions include insurance firms, venture capitalists, currency exchanges, some microloan organizations, and pawn shops. These non-bank financial institutions provide services that are not necessarily suited to banks, serve as competition to banks, and specialize in sectors or groups. Nonbank Financial Institutions. The nonbank financial sector comprises a plethora of different types of institutions with varying degrees of importance and varied contributions to the economy. On the whole, such institutions are relatively unimportant in the Mongolian financial sector. As of 2007, there were 137 registered finance companies, of which 102 were engaged in lending—comprising less than 2 percent of all financial system assets. These NBFIs are widely mixed in corporate culture, capabilities, and depth and breadth of outreach. Portfolio quality and return on assets in both credit unions and NBFIs range from excellent to technically insolvent. Core target markets for both of these types of institutions vary from highly privileged clients to poor and vulnerable non poor clients. One NBFIs of particular importance for micro- and rural finance is Credit Mongol, which was founded by four local NGOs. The institution has received most of its capital from donor agencies, especially the European Union.

Figure 1. Financial Institutions in Mongolia, 2019-2021 (Source: Net open position-to-capital ratio improved, indicating mitigation of FX risk)

2.2. Empirical results

The nations studied were chosen using the classification system used in the IMF's 2005 World Economic Outlook report. Patrick (1966) predicted that a transition from capital widening to capital deepening would occur over time in an early work. Liang and Reichert (2007) found evidence that as a country's degree of economic development rises, the relative importance of bank-based to market-based financial sector drivers of economic growth shifts. Furthermore, the relative role of banks vs. non-bank financial institutions (NBFIs), such as insurance firms, may shift. As a result, one would expect the relationship between financial sector structure and economic growth rate to fluctuate over time, implying that pooling the data sample may not be suitable; thus, separate models for developed and developing market countries are estimated. Countries are divided into two groups by the IMF: advanced economies and emerging economies. There are 29 countries classified as advanced, and 146 countries labeled as emerging. The data for this study comes from the 2005 World Bank Economic Indicators report, which covers the years 1960 to 2004, as well as Beck, Demirguc-Kunt, and Levine's data set (1999). The World Bank does not collect all the data itself but relies upon a variety of data sources. The World Bank makes a determined effort to insure that the

data are defined and collected as comparably between countries and over time as possible. To ensure a balanced panel design, only countries with reported data for all the variables and for all years are included in the estimation sample. Thus, for some of the countries and for certain models, there was missing data for selected variables and years; hence, the final sample of countries will vary by model. In Table 3, the first column labeled 'Panel(s)' indicates which of the three models/panels (A, B, or C) and reported in subsequent tables where each country has been included in the estimation sample.

2.2.1. Domestic credit to private sector as share of GDP

The multi-variable Johansen cointegration approach was used to examine the long-run influence of bank loans on economic growth in Ethiopia, and it was discovered that there is a positive and direct link between those variables (Murty, Sailaja, & Demissie, 2012). Through the efficient distribution of available financial resources, bank loans to the private sector influence economic growth. As a result, decision-makers must consider the importance of the banking and financial sectors in increasing capital, which is one of the elements of production, as well as expanding domestic investment. The research, by Alves which defined the impact of public debt on the economic growth of Mongolia from 1974 till 2012 using non-linear method tells us that the optimal debt ratio is around 75%, and if it exceeds it, debt service costs can have a negative effect on GDP growth (Alves & Afonso, 2015). Similarly, bank loans to the private sector will boost output and have a limited positive impact on the entire economy. Excessing the ideal ratio can increase interest costs and have a negative impact on overall production.

2.2.2. Financial system deposits as share of GDP

According to He, Lu, and Mano's study, China's huge national savings, which are among the highest in the world, enhance domestic investment and accelerate the country's economic growth. In such a circumstance, the country's government are attempting to lower high savings by encouraging domestic consumption in order to achieve long-term social growth, diminish economic bubbles, and eliminate inequality (He, Lu, & Mano, 2018). However, most countries are pursuing a policy which is from exactly opposite point of view to China's intentions to reduce investment and to keep its economic growth at a controlled level. Due to the lack of investment in most developing countries, on the one hand they encourage investments not only more savings. But on the other hand they comply with lower consumption to support domestic accumulation. Hundie found in his study that there is a long-term positive direct relationship between savings and gross domestic investment, and also the long-term effect of savings on total investment is stronger than the short-term effect (Hundie, 2016). For that reason, it's necessary to maintain the ratio of deposits to GDP as high as possible.

2.2.3. Economic growth

Economic growth is defined as an increase in the volume of production in a particular year over the previous year. However, economic growth and development entail not only quantitative but also qualitative improvements, such as the reduction of poverty in the economy and society, the creation of new jobs, and an increase in GDP per capita (Ivic, 2015). The growth of those quantitative and qualitative indicators influences the country's residents' standard of life, thus the country's authorities must consider the implications of their policy on this subject. Activities of non-bank financial institutions (NBFI) expanded despite the economic turbulence, as their loans reached 4.6 percent of GDP by December 2021 (figure 2).

Figure 2. Mongolia: Gross Domestic Product, 1981-1996 (Source: Ministry of Finance and Economy of Mongolia)

2.3. Financial efficiency

A very profitable financial organization cannot be said to be running efficiently. This is because, despite being a good financial institution, an inefficiently operated organization may be able to operate efficiently in the event of temporary economic shocks, or the organization may experience losses owing to the detrimental effects of the external environment. The efficiency of financial institutions and markets is seen below.

Figure 3. a. Bank net interest margin (%), b. Bank overhead costs to total assets (Source: Worldbank, Global)

2.4. Financial Database & Estimates of Researchers

The net interest margin and bank overhead costs to total assets represent the bank's financial efficiency. As countries' income levels rise, the net interest margin shrinks. Higher operational profit might occur in low-income countries due to limited bank competition and the difficulties of entering new markets. Mongolia's banking sector has a small net interest margin compared to high-income countries. The same pattern holds true for operational costs, as seen in Figure 4, where the banking sector's efficiency in low-income countries is generally low.

Figure 4. Stock market turnover ratio (%) (Source: Worldbank, Global Financial Database & Estimates of Researchers)

The stock market turnover ratio in low-income countries is 3.3%, while in high-income countries it is 53.3%, however stock market activity and profitability are low in Mongolia)

2.5. Financial stability

Financial stability is critical for macroeconomic stability, and experts are investigating it thoroughly. The Altman Z-score is the most often used metric for determining the viability of financial organizations. Ratios including equity ratios, non-performing loans, and liquidity ratios are used to assess the financial institution's long-term viability for the same reason.

Figure 5. A. Bank Z-score. B. Stock price volatility (Source: Worldbank, Global Financial Database & Estimates of Researchers)

2.6. Financial Depth

According to figure 6, a country's financial depth is assessed in a variety of methods, with the goal of comparing the total banks and other financial institutions to the country's economic production. Financial Depth (The World Bank, 2016)

Figure 6. Domestic credit to the private sector as a share of GDP in Mongolia. Private credit to GDP ratio (Statista, 2020).

2.7. Growing importance of non-bank financial institutions.

Risks from volatile credit growth in Mongolia are further complicated by the growing importance of non-bank financial institutions (NBFIs). While banks are the main providers of private credit, loans by NBFIs increased as a share of GDP from 1.2 percent in 2010 to about 3.7 percent in September 2019 (loans increased by almost 13 times, from about MnT 100 billion to about MnT 1.3 trillion during this period). While this sector is too small to constitute a systemic risk, vulnerabilities of NBFIs should be closely monitored and addressed as NBFIs largely serve the riskier part of the population. 33 Particularly, following the macroprudential measures by the BoM since mid-2018, credit (especially individual loans) may have gradually migrated to the less regulated non-banking sectors, including NBFIs. Thus, regulation and supervision of the NBFIs need to be strengthened and, if possible, coverage of macroprudential limits should be expanded to NBFIs.

Figure 7. Growing importance of non-bank financial institutions (NBFIs) (Source: BoM)

2.8. Remittance in Mongolia:

Table 1. Remittance in Mongolia (\$ millions) (Source: World Bank, 2020, “Migration and Remittances in Mongolia,” in “Migration and Remittances Factbook,” Development Prospects Group, World Bank, Washington, DC)

3. Discussion

How do these findings square with Allen et al. (2005)'s claim that China's financial sector is weak and does not foster growth? Mongolian financial institutions clearly have inefficiencies that are not present in their international equivalents. Mongolian banks, however, have benefited substantially from financial reforms in comparison to other domestic financial institutions, and have grown dramatically from just giving policy loans to distributing money and managing projects according to commercial norms. It's difficult to believe that such advancements had no impact on Mongolia's rapid growth. Beyond the discussion in the third section on why banks may outperform non-banks, there are three additional facts worth mentioning.

1. Banks perform better than non-banks because they enjoy a better pool of borrow-ers. Borrowers prefer to borrow from banks because bank loans, especially short-term loans, are less costly than other financial instruments. Among those best candidates, banks typically pick up the most substantial borrowers with collateral (see Appendix for two surveys of firms’ financing patterns in China). This may also be a reason banks increased their relative exposure towards the financing of private firms, even though most financed private firms were large. It appears “chasing the winners” is a good strategy for Chinese banks.

2. Financing the state-owned sector per se does not necessarily imply misallocation of capital. The state-owned sector has accounted for around 40% of GDP growth in recent years (Sun, 2004). As banks can to some extent screen good borrowers from bad and allocate the capital to profitable state-owned enterprises (Cull and Xu, 2000), bank loans are still important in supporting local industrial growth.

3. Banks with many branches all around the country make it easier to share the credit records of clients and benefit from industry expertise than their standing alone counterparts, especially in China, which still lacks efficient information sharing mechanisms.

The analysis revealed a set of urgent problems in the non-banking sector of the Russian financial market. Most of them are due to the gap between the development of individual sectors of this market and the entire national economy, as well as the unfavorable dynamics of the incomes of Russian citizens.

Structural and institutional problems of the Russian economy noticeably limit investment opportunities and narrow the range of relevant instruments (although the Bank of Russia as a whole has created conditions for financial investment in Russia). On the other hand, the formation and growth of savings are restrained by social problems, which is reflected not only in the resource base of pension and investment funds. Thus, the solution to the problems of development of organizations in the non-banking segment of the Russian financial market goes beyond the problems of this market and is also ensured by the implementation of measures in general in the field of economic policy. The necessary conditions for turning this segment into an effective mechanism for capital formation and increasing private savings should be:

- Increasing public confidence in the financial market and in the state as a guarantor of the implementation of legislation;
- Increasing the level of protection of the rights and legitimate interests of investors;
- Development of a system of voluntary pension savings, including securing the ownership of pension savings for future retirees; carrying out the privatization of state-owned enterprises and shareholdings, using mechanisms aimed at limiting the concentration of ownership and increasing competition;
- Focus on advanced foreign practices to ensure transparency of information about financial instruments and products for making investment decisions.

The recommended solutions place a focus on institutional reforms and improving the efficiency of interim measures for the market's already adopted development directions. We do not discount the need of relaxing monetary policy conditions through consistent achievement of the proclaimed price objective, as well as the need for further digital modernization of financial market processes. However, these measures only form the necessary, but not sufficient, conditions for the transformation of the financial market into a factor of positive, sustainable macroeconomic and social dynamics. This is confirmed by the pronounced gap that exists today between financial development, which is provided mainly by the banking system, and the state of the real sector of the economy, the social sphere. Elimination of this dichotomy seems to be possible on the basis of a more active role in the financial development of organizations that accumulate resources on a long-term basis, which in turn requires political, institutional, and instrumental solutions in combination with a balanced economic policy. Furthermore, the social impact of the financial market's development in the examined industry should not be overlooked. From a strategic standpoint, it establishes the groundwork for lowering social disparity and establishing proper safeguards, which is critical given the highly inconsistent and sometimes ineffectual nature of Russian authorities' pension decisions over the last two decades.

4. Materials and Methods

The Many empirical studies have attempted to analyze and measure the contribution to growth that financial institutions provide (see Ang 2008; Baltagi, Demetriades, and Law 2009; De Gregorio and Guidotti 1995; Jalilian and Kirkpatrick 2002; King and Levine 1993a, 1993b; Odedokun 1996). In these studies, authors measure financial development by using aggregate financial or monetary variables such as the ratio of M2 to GDP (King and Levine

1993a), the M3 to GDP ratio (Khan and Senhadji 2000), gross domestic savings to GDP (Hassan and al. 2011), banks' deposits or assets over GDP, and private credit by banks over GDP (Levine, Loayza, and Beck 2000) or liquid liabilities to GDP. MFIs worldwide. Thus, it is frequently used as the main data source for many relevant studies on microfinance (see, for instance, Cull and al. 2007; Hermes and al. 2011; Vanroose and D'Espallier 2013). Moreover, the MIX scales institutions with regard to the quality of the MFIs' reporting after being audited by third-party accounting firms. Thus, we focused on MFIs that have their financial statements (balance sheet and income statement) audited and certified by chartered accountants and auditors (at diamond level 4) and accredited by rating agencies (at diamond level 5) to assure data dependability (as in Ahlin and al. 2011; Tchuigoua 2011; Lopatta and al. 2017).

Most of the empirical research focuses on the direct relation between FSD and economic growth. Indicators of FSD that have been used in the literature consist of broad measures of banking activity such as the provision of private credit (lending) and measures of liquidity, such as M2 or M3. In addition, some studies go beyond the banking system and examine the role of the stock market in FSD (Levine, 1998; Liang & Reichert, 2010).

Based upon its flexibility and widespread usage, this study adopts Odedokun's neoclassical aggregate production function model to examine the impact of NBFIs on economic growth. While Odedokun's most recent research focuses on the impact of income inequality and international economic aid on economic growth, he published a paper with Jalilian in 2000 which examines the impact of the components of private investment using a generalized Solow model similar to the one employed in his 1996 paper (Jalilian & Odedokun, 2000). Some earlier papers of his employ a similar model to examine the impact of the size of the monetary sector on economic growth among industrial countries Odedokun (1999), the relationship between financial intermediation and economic growth in developing countries Odedokun (1998), and the relative effects of private and public investment on economic growth in developing countries Odedokun(1997). The literature surrounding Solow-type growth models is voluminous and a complete review is beyond the scope of this paper. Some recent papers include Alfo, Giovanni, and Waldmann (2008) who examined cross-country differences to improve an extended Solow growth model, while Philips (2007) examined growth convergence and allowed for heterogeneous technology, and Jeong and Townsend (2007) examined the sources of total factor productivity, including financial deepening and sectoral-Solow model residuals. Finally, Ding and Knight (2009) use an augmented Solow model to evaluate China's dramatic economic growth.

The research methodology was based on the proven positive dependence of gross domestic product dynamics on the financial depth of the economy, identification of the place and role of non-banking segments selected for analysis, dynamic analysis of statistical data and the analytical developments of the Bank of Russia, and the results of scientific and expert research in the field of financial markets. The specificity of the problems of economic growth and financial development, and their conditioning by various, oftendifficult to formalize factors, required the use of such methods as synthesis, analysis, and deduction for research purposes. Historical, logistic and heuristic approaches were also used. Methods of statistical observation, grouping and comparative analysis were used as tools for quantitative analysis.

Non-bank financial institutions, as part of the national savings system, act as institutions competing for free money resources in the economy. The prospects for their development are determined by the possibilities of redistributing these resources on a long-term basis, which, on the one hand, increases the stability of the resource base for investment and, on the other hand, ensures that their clients receive higher incomes. Such opportunities create the conditions for economic growth, which has been confirmed by numerous studies. At the same time, the implementation of these opportunities in emerging market countries, including Russia, is hampered by the continuing high level of uncertainty in economic prospects in the context of macroeconomic instability and poor performance of the implemented regulatory practices. Factors of distrust in the financial market and protection of investors' rights manifest themselves in the same direction. These conditions reinforce the indifference of the financial market, in terms of its non-banking sector, to the impact on it by economic methods. New financial and technological solutions give impulse to the development of this sector, but not to such an extent as to ensure the growth of real and financial investments. In essence, the substantiation of the conditionality of the dynamics of the development of the

non-banking sector of the Russian financial market by circumstances of a non-economic nature is based on the recognition of the insignificance of the factor of economic policy and the technological factor.

The fact that the Russian regulator constantly loosened monetary policy conditions during the time studied in this study, as well as an enormous technical leap in the growth of the financial sector, are reasons for such acknowledgment. The goal of the work was to examine the state and development trends of the autonomous pension and mutual investment funds sectors, to substantiate the most significant elements influencing their dynamics, and to propose alternative remedies in light of these circumstances.

4.1. Financial Development Measurement

According to the World Bank's Global Financial Development Database, four variables are used to determine a country's level of financial development. Stability, depth, efficiency, and accessibility are some of these variables (The World Bank, 2016). Under the two primary financial components of institutions and markets, these factors are measured.

5. Conclusions

Using the ARDL bounds testing approach to cointegration, we evaluated the long-run relationship between per capita real GDP and the NBFIs in Mongolia from 1974 to 2004. The test found that per capita real GDP, NBFIs, investment, trade openness, and employment have a long-term stable relationship. The negative and substantial coefficients of the error correction factors further demonstrate the existence of a stable long run relationship (ECT). The CUSUM and CUSUM of squares stability tests were also used. The test finds no evidence of significant structural instability in the output function's long run coefficients. The estimation results imply that NBFIs, as well as the other variables in the model, play a significant role in explaining fluctuations in Mongolia's long-run per capita real GDP. The most remarkable finding is that non-bank financial institutions have a favorable and considerable impact on Mongolia's long-run per capita real GDP.

The empirical evidence reveals that financial development indicators such as NBFIs, investment, trade openness, and employment are all contributing to future changes in Mongolia's per capita real GDP. Importantly, the findings show that NBFIs are a crucial component of the financial sector, as they are one of the primary channels via which financial resources are successfully routed from savers to users in the economy. As a result, it is critical that the appropriate authorities extensively examine the procedures by which NBFIs supply financial services most effectively in order to support long-term economic growth.

The fact that the Russian regulator constantly loosened monetary policy conditions during the time studied in this study, as well as an enormous technical leap in the growth of the financial sector, are reasons for such acknowledgment. The goal of the work was to examine the state and development trends of the autonomous pension and mutual investment funds sectors, to substantiate the most significant elements influencing their dynamics, and to propose alternative remedies in light of these circumstances. In conclusion, the paper has examined Mongolia's financial sector's steady improvement and development. It has recognized different changes in financial indicators, stating several difficulties dealt with by the government in order to restore regularity and growth to the sector.

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References

Abma, R.C.N. & Fase, M.M.G. (2003). Financial environment and economic growth in selected Asian countries.

- ADB, 2006, "Rural Finance in Mongolia," in "Beyond Microfinance. "Bank Branch Deregulation. Quarterly Journal of Economics 111, 639-670.
- Bank, B., 2007. Non-Bank Financial Institutions in Bangladesh: An Analytical Review. Policy Analysis Unit (PAU). Research Department, Bangladesh Bank, Dhaka.
- Carmichael, Jeffrey, and Michael Pomerleano. 2002. The Development and Regulation of Non-bank Financial Institutions. World Bank, Washington, DC.
- Christian Saborowski, and et al. 2015. Rethinking Financial Deepening: Stability and Growth in Emerging Markets. IMF Staff Discussion Note SDN. No 8. Washington, DC: IMF.
- Čihák, Martin, and Richard Podpiera. 2008. "Integrated Financial Supervision: Which Model?" North American Journal of Economics and Finance 19: 135-52.
- Froot, Kenneth A., Mason, Scott P., Perold, André F., Merton, Robert C., Bodie, Zvi, Sirri, Erik R. & Tufano, Peter (eds.), The Global Financial System: A Functional Perspective. Harvard Business School Press, Boston, MA, 81-128.
- Ivic, M. (2015). Economic Growth and Development. Journal of Process Management – New Technologies, International, Vol. 3, No.1.
- Jayarathne, Jith & Strahan, Philip E., 1996. The Finance-Growth Nexus: Evidence from Journal of Asian Economics 14, 11-21.
- King, R. & Levine, R. (1993). Finance and growth: Schumpeter. Quarterly Journal of Economics, 108, 717-738.
- King, Robert G. & Levine, Ross, 1993a. Finance and Growth: Schumpeter Might Be Right. Quarterly Journal of Economics 108, 717-738.
- King, Robert G. & Levine, Ross, 1993b. Finance, Entrepreneurship and Growth: Theory and Growth. Journal of Monetary Economics 32, 513-542.
- La Porta, Rafael, Lopez-de-Silanes, Florencio, Shleifer, Andrei, & Vishny, Robert W., 1998. Law and Finance. Journal of Political Economy 106, 1113-1150.
- Levine, Ross, Loayza, Norman & Beck, Thorsten, 2000. Financial Intermediation and Growth: Causality and Causes. Journal of Monetary Economics 46, 31-77.
- Levine, Ross & Zervos, Sara, 1998. Stock Markets, Banks, and Economic Growth. American Economic Review 88, 537-558.
- Melecky, Martin, and Anca Podpiera. 2012. "Institutional Structures of Financial Sector Supervision, Their Drivers, and Emerging Benchmark Models." MPRA Paper 37059, University of Munich, Germany.
- Phelps, Edmund S. 2019. The Three Revolutions Economics Needs. Project Syndicate, January 23. Available online: <https://www.project-syndicate.org/commentary/economics-must-change-in-three-ways-by-edmund-s--phelps-2019-01>(accessed on 27 November 2021).
- Rogoff, Kenneth. 2019. Risks to the Global Economy in 2019. Project Syndicate, January 11. Available online: <https://www.project-syndicate.org/commentary/global-economy-main-risks-in-2019-by-kenneth-rogoff-2019-01>(accessed on 27 November 2021).
- Sahay, Ratna, Martin Cihak, Papa N'Diaye, Adolfo Barajas, Diana B. Ayala Pena, Ran Bi, Yuan Gao, Annette J. Kyobe, Lam Nguyen,
- Schumpeter, Joseph A. 1911. A Theory of Economic Development. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Shaw, Edward S., 1973. Financial Deepening in Economic Development. Oxford University Press, New York, NY.
- Sirri, Erik R. & Tufano, Peter, 1995. The Economics of Pooling. In: Crane, Dwight B.,
- Stolbov, Michael. 2008. The influence of the financial market on economic growth in Russia. Economy of the XXI Century, 65-75.
- Sun, Lijian, 2004. Zhongguo Jingrong Tixi de Cuiruo Xing (The Fragility in China's Financial Systems). The Study of Finance and Economics 2004 (1), 61-69.
- Ternovskaya, Elena Petrovna. 2020. Russian mutual funds as a form of collective investment of savings. Economy Business Banks 47:9-20.
- Townsend, Robert M., 1979. Optimal Contracts and Competitive Markets with Costly State Verification. Journal of Economic Theory 21, 265-293.
- Vittas, Dimitri. (1997). The Role of Non-bank Financial Intermediaries in Egypt and other MENA countries. Development Research Group, World Bank.
- Wang, Sangui & Li, Yingxing, 2004. Zhongguo Xibu Diqu Nongcun Xinyongshe de Zhili Jiegou, Xingwei yu Yeji (Managerial Structure, Conduct and Performance of Rural Credit Cooperatives in Western China). Issues in Agricultural Economy 2004 (6), 38-42.

- World Bank. 2012. Global Financial Development Report 2013: Rethinking the Role of the State in Finance. World Bank, Washington, DC (<https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/gfdr>)
- Xie, Ping, 1998. Zhongguo Fei Yinhang Jinrong Jigou Yanjiu (A Study of the Chinese Non-bank Financial Institutions), Journal of Economics and Finance 1998 (3), 3-7, (4), 3-6, (5), 3-7.

